

INTERNET AND INDIAN YOUTH

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Abstract:

Internet World Statistics shows India is on 3rd position in internet usage (also Mobile usage). The Internet itself is not bad; it makes a wealth of information available at an unprecedented rate. But internet is both a boon and bane.

Keywords: *Internet Usage, Internet Addiction, Indian Youth*

Introduction:

In year 2000, the number of internet users in India was 5,000,000. The current "World Internet Statistics" shows that, the number of internet users in India has increased more than 137,000,000. In world, India is on 3rd position with highest number of internet users and in Asia India is on 2nd position.

The state-owned Videsh Sanchar Nigam Limited (VSNL) launched Internet Services in India in August 1995. According to the Internet & Mobile Association of India (IAMAI) the low cost of broadband has helped increase Internet usage. The progress of ICT (INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY) and Broadband policies announced in 1995 helped to grow Internet in India. Nowadays gadgets like mobiles, tablets,

i-pad, smart phones, i-phones have brought revolution in World. Now with the help of various Apps, we can find almost everything with single touch. It is well known fact that as number of internet users increases, the number of “Internet Addicts” also increases. Researches shows that among the internet users and internet addicts, the main age group is youth (age 12-25).

Internet Addiction:

“Internet Addiction Disorder” was originally proposed as a disorder by Ivan Goldberg, M.D., in 1995. He took pathological gambling as diagnosed by the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-IV) as his model for the description of IAD. Internet addiction disorder is not listed in the latest DSM manual (DSM-5, 2013), which is commonly used by psychiatrists. Gambling disorder is the only behavioural (non-substance related) addiction included in DSM-5. So, let us call IAD just a problematic internet use or internet addiction. It is prolong, uncontrolled internet use affecting our personal, family, professional, and social life.

Types of Internet Addictions:

Some scientists distinguish 5 types of internet addiction (given by K.Young):

1. Cyber sexual addiction - irresistible impulse to porn sites and cyber make-up.
2. Virtual dating addiction - a great quantity of internet friends.
3. Obtrusive need of Internet - online gaming, shopping.
4. Obtrusive web-surfing - endless internet searching.
5. PC addiction - obtrusive gaming.

Symptoms - Internet Addiction:

Behavioural:

- Tolerance: a need for markedly increased amount of time online.
- The Internet is accessed more and for longer periods than was intended.
- A great deal of time is spent in activities related to the Internet.
- Lying about the level of use
- Preoccupation with the Internet
- Using the Internet to escape other problems

Physical and Mental:

- Withdrawal syndrome: a reduction of Internet use results in anxiety, obsessive thinking about the Internet, and dreams about the Internet.
- A persistent desire exists to cut down or control Internet use.
- Increases in blood pressure, cardiovascular stress, memory difficulties, lack of concentration, headaches, stomach and muscle pain, and weakened vision
- Lethargy, listlessness, sleeplessness, panic, irritability, and anger

Social:

- Important social, occupational, or recreational activities are given up because of Internet use.
- Increased tension and competition in the workplace; lowered productivity.
- Longer working days and less leisure time

Youth:

Studies conducted all over the world shows that, the most vulnerable group of problematic internet use is youth. The UN, for statistical consistency across regions, defines 'youth', as those persons between the ages of 15 and 24 years, without prejudice to other definitions by Member States. In INDIA more than 50% of the country's population is under the age of 25 years and 70% of the population is under 35.

Indian youth and internet usage:

The youth of India is using the internet as a means of having an active social life. They are using it for commenting, tweeting, liking, poking, re-tweeting, blogging, following. The internet, social media in particular, has become a platform for sharing opinions and views.

The Internet itself is not bad; it makes a wealth of information available at an unprecedented rate. Everyday the Internet is accessed by millions of people gathering information, checking emails, and chatting with people the world over. It can be used anywhere, anytime, any place.

All the aspects of life of a person are getting affected due to excess use of internet. Behaviour, emotional, social, physical changes occurring, and because of this internet addiction is actually bad. Among the internet addicts majority of people belongs to age group of 14-25 yrs(Adolescents and Youth of nation).

Youth is the actual power of any country, they are the one who run nation. So Youth and whole society must think about controlling this internet addiction.

Conclusion:

We need to take action to overcome this impact of internet on our youth. For that we need to train our youth(15-25yrs) for proper use of internet. We must design a good training program for internet usage. This is the need of time, to train our youth to control their internet usage, otherwise the internet will start controlling our youth and in turn society.

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